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**Increasing palmitic acid and reducing stearic acid content of supplemental fatty acid blends
improves production performance of mid-lactation dairy cows**

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INTERPRETATIVE SUMMARY

Increasing palmitic acid and reducing stearic acid content of supplemental fatty acid blends improves production performance of mid-lactation dairy cows. *By Bales et al., page XXX.* The objective of our study was to determine the effects of changing the ratio of palmitic (C16:0) and stearic (C18:0) acids in supplemental fatty acid blends on milk production of mid-lactation dairy cows. Overall fatty acid supplementation increased yields of milk, 3.5% fat corrected milk, energy corrected milk, milk fat, and milk lactose. Increasing level of C16:0 in supplemental fatty acid blends increased dry matter intake, fat corrected milk, energy corrected milk, and milk fat yield. Mid-lactation dairy cows producing ~40-50 kg/d of milk benefited most with a ratio of 80% C16:0 and 10% C18:0.

Supplemental Table S1. Milk fatty acid content for cows fed treatment diets (n = 24)

Variable	Treatment ²				SEM ³	Contrast ⁴		
	CON	L-PA	M-PA	H-PA		CON vs FAT	Linear	Quadratic
Summation by source, g/100 g								
De novo	28.1	26.3	25.8	25.8	0.25	<.001	0.01	0.12
Mixed	38.3	37.5	39.4	40.6	0.34	<.001	<.001	0.05
Preformed	33.5	35.8	34.8	33.5	0.29	<.001	<.001	0.73
Selected individual fatty acids, g/100 g								
C4:0	3.21	3.34	3.29	3.27	0.06	<0.01	0.01	0.63
C6:0	2.24	2.21	2.17	2.17	0.03	<0.01	0.01	0.17
C8:0	1.37	1.29	1.26	1.26	0.02	<0.01	0.01	0.16
C10:0	3.51	3.15	3.07	3.09	0.06	<0.01	0.12	0.09
C12:0	4.20	3.66	3.56	3.60	0.08	<0.01	0.25	0.07
C14:0	12.5	11.8	11.5	11.4	0.12	<0.01	<0.01	0.18
C16:0	36.8	36.1	37.9	39.1	0.31	<0.01	<0.01	0.07
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	1.52	1.42	1.50	1.56	0.08	0.09	<0.01	0.41
C18:0	8.19	9.49	8.88	8.27	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	0.98
<i>trans</i> -6 to -8 C18:1	0.22	0.26	0.25	0.23	0.004	<0.001	<0.001	0.95
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	0.15	0.19	0.17	0.16	0.003	<0.001	<0.001	0.89
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	0.33	0.36	0.34	0.32	0.02	0.01	<0.001	0.78
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	0.56	0.55	0.54	0.53	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.99
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	16.0	17.3	17.1	16.7	0.19	<0.001	<0.001	0.27
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	2.13	2.02	2.01	2.05	0.03	<0.001	0.10	0.10
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15 C18:3	0.38	0.35	0.34	0.34	0.005	<0.001	0.03	0.02

¹Experimental diets fed to 24 cows in replicated 4 × 4 Latin squares with 21-d periods and balanced for carryover effects. Samples and data for production variables collected during the last 5 d of each treatment period (d 17 to 21).

²CON = Non- fatty acid (FA) supplemented control; L-PA = 1.5% of DM to provide approximately 30% C16:0 + 50% C18:0, M-PA = 1.5% of DM to provide approximately 50% C16:0 + 30% C18:0, and H-PA = 1.5% of DM to provide approximately 80% C16:0 + 10% C18:0.

³Greatest SEM.

⁴CON vs. FAT, linear, and quadratic contrasts tested the overall effect of FA supplementation and the effects of increasing the level of C16:0 in FA blends.

Supplement Table S2. Blood metabolites for cows fed treatment diets (n=24)¹

Variable	Treatment				SEM ³	Contrasts ⁴		
	CON	L-PA	M-PA	H-PA		CON vs FAT	Linear	Quadratic
Insulin, ug/L	0.76	0.74	0.72	0.76	0.08	0.32	0.55	0.14
NEFA ⁵ , mEq/L	0.09	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.003	<0.001	0.48	0.19
BHB, mg/dL	8.36	8.28	8.6	8.43	0.24	0.62	0.42	0.46

¹Experimental diets fed to 24 cows in replicated 4 × 4 Latin squares with 21-d periods and balanced for carryover effects. Samples and data for production variables collected during the last 5 d of each treatment period (d 17 to 21).

²CON = Non- fatty acid (FA) supplemented control; L-PA = 1.5% of DM to provide approximately 30% C16:0 + 50% C18:0, M-PA = 1.5% of DM to provide approximately 50% C16:0 + 30% C18:0, and H-PA = 1.5% of DM to provide approximately 80% C16:0 + 10% C18:0.

³Greatest SEM.

⁴CON vs. FAT, linear, and quadratic contrasts tested the overall effect of FA supplementation and the effects of increasing the level of C16:0 in FA blends.

⁵Nonesterified fatty acids